

Privacy by Design in U.S. Project Development: Legal Myth or Emerging Obligation?

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Abstract

Privacy by Design is increasingly a highly debated principle in international privacy law mainly after it was incorporated into the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the EU region. Nevertheless, its standing regarding U.S. project development is unclear, which is why important questions arise about whether Privacy by Design obligations are implicitly mandated by U.S. privacy laws. This paper aims to assess how the CCPA and the CPRA require Privacy by Design practices in planning and managing projects. Based on a review of the contemporary legal tone, the article provides analyses of Privacy by Design arguing that even though not currently a legal mandate for companies operating in the U.S., it is becoming more of a business necessity due to rising regulatory actions and litigation costs. This paper analyzes new jurisprudence organized enforcement, current paradigms, and legislative initiatives to review whether Privacy by Design is transitioning to a principled legally enforceable duty under US Privacy law.

I. Introduction

Privacy by Design, coined by Dr. Ann Cavoukian in the 1990s, is based on the idea that the protection of privacy should be integrated into the design phase of goods and services offered to the public.¹ Despite being regarded as an optimal solution for managing information in the workplace, its legal admissibility under US law is questionable. Unlike the GDPR where Privacy by Design is established under Article 25, the United States has a fragmented approach towards privacy. The CCPA and CPRA have shifted the privacy paradigm differently but also do not go so far as to mandate Privacy by Design. Moving forward, this article analyses whether there is an implicit requirement for Privacy by Design through an analysis of legislative purpose, regulatory understandings, and judicial opinions.

The advancement of the new economy and the spread of data technologies has increased consumer concern over privacy. The firms are increasingly experiencing pressure in how they internally implement privacy aspects into their tactical business plans.² As the stewardship of big data becomes centralized, regulatory bodies like the Federal Trade Commission (FTC) and the California Privacy Protection Agency (CPPA) are heaping pressure on organizations mainly due to the lack of adequate anticipatory controls in data management.³ This emerging legal environment indicates that while Privacy by Design, is possibly not a legal requirement, any

¹ Ann Cavoukian, *Privacy by Design: The 7 Foundational Principles* (2009), <https://www.ipc.on.ca/wp-content/uploads/resources/7foundationalprinciples.pdf> (last visited Oct. 12, 2024).

² Eric Everson, *Privacy by Design: Taking Ctrl of Big Data*, 65 *Clev. St. L. Rev.* 27 (2017), <https://engagedscholarship.csuohio.edu/clevstlrev/vol65/iss1/6/> (last visited Jan. 28, 2025).

³ Federal Trade Commission, *Protecting Consumer Privacy in an Era of Rapid Change: Recommendations for Businesses and Policymakers* (2012), <https://www.ftc.gov/reports/protecting-consumer-privacy-era-rapid-change-recommendations-businesses-policymakers> (last visited Nov. 6, 2024).

organization that does not implement it places itself in a vulnerable position of facing charges, fines, and most importantly, damage to its reputation.⁴

Similarly, various consumer organizations and privacy scholars argue that Privacy by Design is necessary to overcome the fundamental privacy risks characteristic of modern media.

Incorporating privacy during the first stages of systems development instead of using it as an afterthought reduces risk and improves the reliability of technology, consumer confidence, and compliance with legal standards.⁵ It also raises the question of whether Privacy by Design has more to do with legal compliance or operational management more and more in industries dealing with sensitive data such as finance, healthcare, and e-commerce. This is where the application of Privacy by Design and the assessment of the legislative implied requirements pose a greater challenge, particularly for corporate America.

II. The Evolution of Privacy by Design in the U.S. Legal Framework

1. Federal Initiatives and the Absence of a National Mandate

Currently, the United States does not have a unified federal privacy law like the GDPR.

While certain federal laws include privacy considerations like the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) or the Federal Trade Commission (FTC) Act, nothing mandates Privacy by Design compliance. Nevertheless, the FTC has embraced

⁴ European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA), *Privacy and Data Protection by Design – From Policy to Engineering* (Jan. 2020), <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/privacy-and-data-protection-by-design> (last visited Sep. 20, 2024).

⁵ Gartner, *Upholding Privacy by Design*, <https://www.gartner.com/en/legal-compliance/trends/upholding-privacy-by-design> (last visited Feb. 5, 2025).

Privacy by Design as a best practice in enforcement actions and guidance documents.^{6,7} Currently, there is no federal Privacy by-design requirement for US government information systems, however, NIST and the Department of Homeland Security have offered frameworks that promote privacy by design. For instance, the NIST Privacy Framework can be used to help organizations incorporate privacy protection into their systems, thus strengthening Privacy by Design principles while not being legally mandated.⁸

The emergence of the American Data Privacy Protection Act (ADPPA) in recent legislation suggests that a federal privacy regime is gaining increasing attention. Despite the debate around the effectiveness of the ADPPA, there are measures on data minimization and protection of consumer data rights that could contribute to the enforcement of Privacy by Design principles indirectly.⁹ Executive orders about AI and cybersecurity, particularly where the focus is made on consumer data protection, hint at a more stringent federal protectionism. These tentative instruments, if implemented, could become precursors to the Privacy by Design regime on the national level.¹⁰

The lack of a single unified federal law that requires Privacy by Design means that as regulations become even more fragmented at the state, it is vital for businesses to embrace Privacy by Design principles preemptively. Several states are also enacting their privacy

⁶ Federal Trade Commission, *supra* note 3.

⁷ International Association of Privacy Professionals (IAPP), *Designing for Privacy: 2023 Report on Privacy by Design Implementation*, <https://iapp.org/resources/article/designing-for-privacy-2023/> (last visited Dec. 1, 2024).

⁸ Cavoukian, *supra* note 1.

⁹ *Nd.*

¹⁰ Everson, *supra*, 2.

laws, based on the CCPA and the GDPR or other models. This patchwork of regulations necessitates Privacy by Design to be placed not only as a practical reality to deal with multiple sets of standards across states, in the first place even if no universal standard at the federal level exists.

2. CCPA and CPRA: De Facto Privacy by Design?

While the CCPA focuses on consumer rights concerning personal information, the CPRA lays out responsibilities that are in line with Privacy by Design principles.¹¹ The California Privacy Rights Act of 2020 creates the California Privacy Protection Agency (CPPA) which has the power to prescribe regulations that may implement the Privacy by Design requirements. More extensively, the CPRA requires risk assessments and data minimization, both of which, indirectly, require the implementation of Privacy by Design. Furthermore, where the CPRA requires businesses to perform periodic security assessments, it again underscores that privacy concerns must be inherent from the initial stage of data processing.¹²

Furthermore, the reference to consumer opt-out rights and obligations regarding automated decision-making presents the need for privacy measures at the design phase as evidenced by the CPRA. Organizations that cannot meet these requirements will face non-compliance which makes Privacy by Design relevant even in the absence of statutory requirements.¹³

CPRA over time may undergo further amendments and enforcement actions, and Privacy by Design could become an accepted compliance requirement.

¹¹ Cavoukian, *supra* note 1.

¹² TechTarget, *The Intersection of Privacy by Design and Privacy Engineering* (Nov. 29, 2021), <https://www.techtarget.com/searchsecurity/feature/The-intersection-of-privacy-by-design-and-privacy-engineering> (last visited Apr. 4, 2025).

¹³ ENISA, *supra* note 4.

The implementation of CPRA regulations has also brought in the compliance culture that focuses on privacy integration at the concept phase.¹⁴ Companies in California are expected to operate under the new legal model which outlines that such measures can reduce enforcement risks. The focus on accountability mechanisms, such as privacy impact assessments under the CPRA fosters companies to embrace Privacy by Design as a business advantage in the long-term strategy rather than a compliance issue.

3. Litigation Trends and Regulatory Enforcement

Various judgments and regulatory activities regarding data protection have shifted focus to the need to adopt preventive measures. Cases such as *United States v. Facebook, Inc.* (2021) show how courts are increasingly concerned with companies' data protection policies and examples such as Privacy by Design.¹⁵ Moreover, in data breach cases like *People v. Sephora USA, Inc.*, No. 22STCV25195 (Cal. Super. Ct. filed Aug. 24, 2022), there are expectations of business to incorporate privacy provisions at the design phase of the information system, not after a data breach had already occurred.¹⁶

As the number of CCPA and CPRA class-action lawsuits increases, companies build privacy controls into their infrastructure. When firms have not provided sufficient privacy measures, courts have favored plaintiffs, further underlining the requirement of Privacy by Design as a

¹⁴ Law Society, *Implementing Privacy by Design Principles in Legal Frameworks* (Oct. 15, 2023), <https://lawsociety.blog/privacy-by-design-principles/> (last visited Apr. 2, 2025).

¹⁵ Natalie Purcell. "United States v. Facebook, Inc.-456 F. Supp. 3d 115 (DDC 2020)." *Intell. Prop. & Tech. LJ* 25 (2020): 191. <https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/iprop25&div=22&id=&page=>

¹⁶ Liubov Kirzhakova. "Facial Recognition Technology in the Market: What Consumers Need to Know to Protect Their Rights." *UC Law Science and Technology Journal* 16, no. 1 (2024): 1. MITRE, *Demystifying Privacy by Design* (Aug. 14, 2013), <https://www.mitre.org/news-insights/publication/demystifying-privacy-design> (last visited Aug. 23, 2024).

legal liability precaution measure.¹⁷ Altogether, state attorneys general have been using consumer protection laws to sanction organizations with unfair data practices, thus establishing Privacy by Design as a best practice among organizations.

Moreover, legal enforcement at this level instituted strict penalties for consumer privacy violations as other aspects such as large-scale data breaches and consumer litigation have increased companies' awareness of the financial and reputational costs of privacy negligence. Some companies decided to use Privacy by Design voluntarily because they have realized that addressing privacy issues at early stages of development can prevent those companies from having to pay million-dollar lawsuits, losing their reputation, or having to pay large fine fees to regulatory bodies.¹⁸ This shift points our attention to the fact that there is more general pressure on using Privacy by Design at the organizational level, outside of legal reasons.

II. Legal Analysis: Is Privacy by Design an Emerging Obligation?

Privacy by Design is gradually emerging in the United States as a best practice despite having no statutory backing. Several legal principles inherent in contemporary privacy legislation and enforcement actions indicate that Privacy by Design as an approach to data management is becoming more widely considered requisite.¹⁹

Perhaps the most straightforward evidence to that effect is purpose limitation and data minimization as has been outlined in the CPRA. This regulation also provides that businesses

¹⁷ Law Society, *Implementing Privacy by Design Principles in Legal Frameworks*, *supra* note 14.

¹⁸ ENISA, *supra* note 4.

¹⁹ Cavoukian, *supra* note 1.

should only collect the data that is relevant for a particular function and store or process it for as long as is reasonable. These constraints correspond with Privacy by Design's principles directly as they advocate for the privacy of data from the time it is collected.²⁰ Businesses based in California must therefore adopt Privacy by Design principles regardless of whether they are so named, to align their practices with the state laws.²¹

Another promising development in the U.S. law that implies Privacy by Design implementation is Security by Design. New cases of inadequate data security have been brought to the attention of the Federal Trade Commission (FTC), due to negligence in practicing preventive measures to mitigate breaches and unauthorized access.²² Across various enforcement actions, the FTC has made it clear that it is essential to build security elements into a product or service right from the onset and not as an add-on feature. Despite not being marked as Privacy by Design, these enforcement patterns suggest that privacy and security should be an intrinsic part of the design and build of computer systems.

Also, algorithmic accountability laws and new AI laws/regulations at the federal and state levels indicate that policymakers are expecting privacy considerations to be integrated during the development of ADMs.²³ Possibilities regarding anti-bias laws, the protection of data in machine learning, and consumer rights concerning automation and AI enhance the

²⁰ Muharem Kianieff, *The Evolution of Consumer Privacy Law: How Privacy by Design Can Benefit from Insights in Commercial Law and Standardization*, 10 *Can. J.L. & Tech.* 1 (2012), <https://ojs.library.dal.ca/CJLT/article/view/4830> (last visited Apr. 1, 2025).

²¹ Kirzhakova, *supra* note 16.

²² Federal Trade Commission, *supra* note 3.

²³ ENISA, *supra* note 4.

implementation of Privacy by Design in AI management systems. These trends support the thesis of this paper that Privacy by Design has emerged as a crucial compliance tool over time and with the increasing complexity of technology regulations.

Comparatively, therefore, the GDPR is relatively prescriptive on Privacy by Design under Article 25, hence useful for benchmarking purposes.²⁴ Contrary to the GDPR, the CPRA does not emphasize built-in privacy and control mechanisms like controllers are expected to demonstrate in response to the law.²⁵ At the same time, Privacy by Design principles are further reflected in CPRA provisions, though based on the regulator's guidance and not legal wording. There are disparities in enforcement mechanisms as well; while the GDPR has hefty fines for noncompliance, the CPPA is still implementing its regulatory framework. Nonetheless, the recent stricter regulatory trend for data protection in the US implies a more explicit shift to Privacy by Design trends.²⁶

Major corporations have adjusted to these legal and regulatory developments by adopting Privacy by Design into their compliance programs. Nowadays, many organizations carry out PIAs and DPIAs routinely across their products and services, including those that may not have any legal requirements to do so. Moreover, the analysis of legal doctrines and case studies has revealed to legal scholars that Privacy by Design principles are included in sectoral

²⁴ Anna Monreale et al., *Privacy-by-Design in Big Data Analytics and Social Mining*, 3 *EPJ Data Sci.* 10 (2014), <https://epjdatascience.springeropen.com/articles/10.1140/epids/s13688-014-0010-4> (last visited Apr. 4, 2025).

²⁵ Kirzhakova, *supra note 16*.

²⁶ Achim Klabunde, *From Privacy by Design to Data Protection by Design: The Challenges of Turning Good Practice into a Legal Obligation*, USENIX (Aug. 14, 2019), <https://www.usenix.org/conference/usenixsecurity19/presentation/klabunde> (last visited Mar. 3, 2025).

legislation in financial services and healthcare.²⁷ In response, business organizations are deploying PETs such as differential privacy and federated learning to mitigate risks and protect individuals' information. The emerging field of cybersecurity and privacy law only serves to emphasize the obvious need to implement protective measures within the design of systems to reduce legal risk regarding consumer data. As class-action lawsuits and regulatory fines become more frequent, Privacy by Design is no longer an option for best practices but a business imperative for managing risks that may be costly and damaging to brand reputations. If organizations do not include Privacy by Design in their integrated approaches, they may experience increased risk of enforcement actions, higher costs, and legal risks.

IV. Future Trajectories: Toward a Formal Privacy by Design Obligation?

1. Legislative Proposals and Federal Privacy Law Prospects

The proposed legislation in America known as the American Data Privacy Protection Act (ADPPA) provides additional consumer protection that can indirectly underpin Privacy by Design principles. As for the second trend, state-level legislation such as the CCPA has begun to incorporate aspects of Privacy by Design.²⁸ Despite the patchy implementation of Privacy by Design principles in regions with federal privacy laws such as the USA, if laws

²⁷ Stuart L. Pardau & Blake Edwards, *The FTC, the Unfairness Doctrine, and Privacy by Design: New Legal Frontiers in Cybersecurity*, 12 *J. Bus. & Tech. L.* 227 (2017), <https://digitalcommons.law.umaryland.edu/jbtl/vol12/iss2/5/> (last visited Nov. 22, 2024).

²⁸ Cavoukian, *supra* note 1.

like ADPPA come into force, it will create national standards of Privacy by Design, which will require organizations to incorporate privacy into all phases of data processing. This may result in the reinforcement of Compliance objectives and the defining of Enduring norms and rules around Privacy by Design.²⁹

The fact that privacy concerns are being addressed presently at both federal and state levels indicates that the passage of federal legislation is near imminent. Pressure from various consumer protection organizations coupled with the emergence of data brokers led to federal legislation for a unified approach. Further, the integration of Privacy by Design with contemporary fields such as artificial intelligence and biometric data collection exposes the inadequacy of the existing laws. Businesses would also require adopting privacy by design into their product life cycle to meet the emergent laws regarding the protection of personal information.³⁰

As of now, ADPPA is still pending in the legislature, but its provisions are friendly to DP principles particularly on data minimization, consumer rights, and accountability. However, if approved, it could lead to a legal requirement for corporations throughout various industries to implement Privacy by Design.³¹ In addition, state-level privacy laws like the California CPRA, Virginia CDPA, and Colorado Privacy Act are also gradually incorporating Privacy by Design principles. This fragmented but progressive approach at the state level may push federal action across the country as enterprises demand a cohesive regulatory policy.

²⁹ ENISA, *supra* note 4.

³⁰ Kirzhakova, *supra* note 16.

³¹ Kianieff, *supra* note 20.

2. Corporate and Technological Drivers

There is a clear business rationale for adopting Privacy by Design based on increased consumer trust, compliance, and risk management. The previous decade saw corporations start adopting Privacy by Design not only as a compliance tool but as a strategic necessity.³² Consumers who are concerned with their privacy are more likely to follow and patronize brands that prioritize their privacy rights. Also, innovations in PETs including homomorphic encryption, differential privacy, and decentralized identity management are emerging to shape the operationalization of Privacy by Design.³³ These technologies are useful in helping organizations to build systems with privacy as a priority while at the same time providing functionality and usability not compromised.

Industry self-regulation is also increasingly being practiced as a control approach within organizations. Several firms in the technology industry are implementing Privacy by Design principles ostensibly to manage risks resulting from data losses and regulatory compliance concerns. They include Global Privacy Control and the rising AI solutions for privacy compliance, which point to the convergence of novelty and Privacy by Design.³⁴ In addition, more companies have their privacy officers and compliance departments providing for Privacy by Design frameworks as part of their firm's compliance guidelines to factor in privacy throughout the design lifecycle.

³² Monreale et al., *supra* note 24.

³³ Klabunde, *supra* note 26.

³⁴ Barredo Arrieta, Alejandro, Natalia Díaz-Rodríguez, Javier Del Ser, Adrien Bennetot, Siham Tabik, Alberto Barbado, Salvador Garcia, et al. (2020). "Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI): Concepts, Taxonomies, Opportunities and Challenges toward Responsible AI." *Information Fusion* 58 (1): 82–115.

It is safe to argue that Privacy by Design, being already widely discussed and recommended by regulatory bodies, may become a standard practice shortly due to constant changes in the regulatory environment and advances in technology. Of notable benefit is that organizations that have embraced Privacy by Design will remain ready to adapt to subsequent changes in regulation, manage compliance risks, and cultivate customer confidence.

V. Conclusion

Though Privacy by Design is not an official legal requirement in the United States, it has become normalized within compliant and jurisprudential standards. The larger complex formed by the CPRA, FTC enforcement actions, and state-level privacy laws contextualizes Privacy by Design as a compliance necessity. Considering the legislative initiatives and increased regulatory activity, Privacy by Design can be expected to become more of a defined need in the future.³⁵

Many organizations have to incorporate Privacy by Design into their development projects as a way of meeting new legal requirements and avoiding compliance issues. In addition, organizations that implement Privacy by Design strategies will be in a better position than their counterparts since consumers will trust them with their data, businesses will have fewer legal obligations in handling consumer data and will be in direct compliance with the market trends.

Looking into the future, data privacy issues will remain a serious concern due to developments in technology. AI, biometric data, and the IoT have continued to grow significantly, raising the following key privacy concerns that require preemptive measures. Privacy by Design thus

³⁵ Monreale et al., *supra note 24*.

provides a life cycle solution to these challenges as it enshrines the principles of privacy at the design level. Non-implementation of Privacy by Design may lead to more regulatory examinations, legal penalties, and negative perceptions by the public.³⁶

Also, the influence of consumers in the determination of privacy practices cannot be overemphasized. Self-awareness of data rights leads to a preference for businesses that respect and uphold these rights.³⁷ Hence, organizations that embrace Privacy by Design not only implement legal and regulatory requirements but also secure competitive and customer advantages. Thus, investing in Privacy by Design is a legal mandate that also makes good business sense in a world where data breaches and privacy violations can do significant financial and reputational damage.³⁸

Thus, though the legal standing of Privacy by Design in the U.S. is still somewhat ambiguous, it is, however, apparent that the concept is highly relevant. The combined external pressure from regulations, consumers, and technology will increase the probability of Privacy by Design from being a best practice into a compliance requirement.³⁹ Understanding the trends and embracing the shift will help organizational leaders prepare for the future and attain long-term success in this new paradigm of privacy.

³⁶ Klabunde, *supra* note 26.

³⁷ Omer Tene & Jules Polonetsky, *Privacy by Design: A Counterfactual Analysis of Google and Facebook Privacy Incidents*, 24 *Berkeley Tech. L.J.* 1333 (2009), https://btjl.org/data/articles2015/vol24/24_4/24-berkeley-tech-lj-1333-2009.pdf (last visited Jan. 10, 2025).

³⁸ Everson, *supra* note 2.

³⁹ Ari Ezra Waldman, *Privacy's Law of Design*, 9 *U.C. Irvine L. Rev.* 1239 (2019), https://digitalcommons.nyls.edu/fac_articles_chapters/1316 (last visited Jul. 18, 2024).

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